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The use of concurrent chemo-irradiation at a patient with non-small cell lung cancer – what after?

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Introduction: Lung cancer represents a diagnostic and a treatment challenge. Diagnostics can be done with bronchoscopy or with a surgical approach, and treatment depending of the histological type and stage can be done with surgery, chemoradiotherapy, radiotherapy alone and targeted or immune therapy.

Material and methods: A male patient aged 63, ECOG PS 0, was hospitalized after a CT scan of the chest where a tumor in the right hilum of the lung was seen (40x31mm) in block with LN p10R which was infiltrating the pericardium. He was diagnosed bronchoscopically, and the biopsy confirmed squamous cell carcinoma stage T4N1M0, which was inoperable.

Results: Due to the stage of the disease, the Multidisciplinary tumor board made the decision to treat the patient with concurrent chemo-radiotherapy. After concurrent chemoradiotherapy with Cisplatin/Etoposide and radiotherapy TD 54Gy/27 fractions was finished, the tumor tissue was further tested for PD-L1 which showed 1% positivity. Control CT scans after chemoradiotherapy showed a partial response with the tumor size decreased to 34mm without metastasis in other organs, and the patient started maintenance treatment with Durvalumab immunotherapy. The patient received C8 till September 2024, and control CT scans show a stable disease with the patient still ECOG PS 0. Conclusion: Diagnostics and treatment with an individual approach to every patient, as well as using concurrent chemoradiotherapy with maintenance immunotherapy can prolong the survival of patients with lung cancer.

Keywords: lung cancer, chemoradiotherapy, immunotherapy, targeted therapy, treatment

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